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Depression and Burnout Levels of Graduate Students in Music

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Abstract

At the end of the undergraduate process, many students dream of graduate school for self-improvement, career, or status. The idea of going to graduate school and the preparations for it are the beginning of a stressful period. The beginning of the courses, the long thesis writing process, and finally, a new scientific product defended is the end of this stressful period. In this process, many students struggle with psychological problems due to poor stress management. The study aims to determine graduate music students' depression and burnout levels. The data collection tools of the correlational survey design study were Beck Depression Scale (BDS) and Maslach Burnout Inventory-Student Scale (MBI-SS). The study group consisted of 236 graduate students in different departments and institutes in the field of music. According to the research results, it was determined that the general depression status of the students was at the level of moderate mood disturbance, and some groups were found to be at the level of clinical depression according to different variables. It was observed that the student's overall burnout levels were at a medium level, while they were at a low level in emotional exhaustion and depersonalization sub-dimensions. While the burnout levels of the students show a significant difference according to having children, educational status, work status, institutes, and departments, there is no significant difference according to gender, marital status, and age.

Keywords: Music, Graduate, Depression, Burnout, Students

1. Introduction

The most critical 21st-century requirement is the ability to keep up with the rapidly evolving and transforming conjuncture. A new application or method realized in any field is rapidly spreading globally. In this information age, rapidly increasing and spreading information has strengthened competition in business and professional life and made specialization even more critical. (Karaman & Bakırcı, 2010). Universities were established to meet society's need for scientific progress and highly qualified human resources. They have essential responsibilities such as conducting scientific research, producing knowledge and technology, disseminating scientific data, and contributing to national and universal development. Intertwined with society in every field, the university is at the highest level of the education system. While the duties of other system levels are to transfer existing knowledge, the university is mainly responsible for producing, disseminating, and utilizing knowledge (Tuzcu, 2003).

Individuals who complete their university education represent the trained human resources in the relevant field by the outcomes of the programs they study. After completing undergraduate education, individuals transition to postgraduate education per their wishes and tendencies. In the first stage, the person specializes in the relevant field with a master's degree and then a doctorate or proficiency in art education. Postgraduate education aims to

develop faculty members and researchers for higher education (Ünal & İltter, 2010) and to train individuals who can produce, use, criticize, and solve problems with their thinking (Alhas, 2006; Bozan, 2012). Graduate education is a prerequisite for development and progress in music, as in all fields of science. In its broadest sense, music science is a branch of science that systematically examines, researches, develops musical theories, and reports all kinds of music-related information with scientific methods using other disciplines (Karkın, 2021). It is an indisputable fact that music occupies a considerable place in life (Özvein et al., 2021). The most important feature that distinguishes students who continue their education in music-related disciplines from others is that artistic concerns are also involved in the process apart from the scientific process (Baydağ & Başoğlu, 2018; Öz, 2019). Although this anxiety is less pronounced in partly music theory fields, it is palpable in fields related to music performance. The leading causes of musical anxiety were identified as irrationality, perfectionism, or destructive cognition (Stephoe & Fidler, 1987; Tobacyk & Downs, 1986), physiological symptoms such as trembling and palpitations (Lehrer, 1987), and behavioral characteristics such as performance and audience avoidance (Clark & Agras, 1999). In addition to the problems mentioned above, graduate students in the field of music have to deal with common problems in producing a thesis. Research shows that students face many difficulties, such as job, advisor, colleagues, personal life, financial difficulties, and academic difficulties during the thesis writing process (Appel & Dahlgren, 2003; Wright, 2003; Akbulut et al., 2013; Koşar, 2021).

For some students, postgraduate study is an inspiring, attractive, and fulfilling process. For others, however, it is a time of personal sacrifice, divided lives, academic problems, lack of social support, and financial and psychological problems (Arastaman et al., 2020; Appel & Dahlgren, 2003; Jairam & Kahl, 2012; Protivnak & Foss, 2009; Temel & Doğan, 2017). Graduate students who face attrition, inadequacy, and burnout in this process and who intend to leave their programs should be able to cope with these difficulties and manage uncertainties at the beginning of their careers (Castello, 2017). Ülev (2014) mentions that it is inevitable for university students to experience depression, anxiety, and burnout as a result of the increase in stress levels they experience. Considering the difficulties experienced during the thesis writing process (Bahçeçi & Uşengül, 2018; Karadağ et al., 2018; Seçer, 2021; Özmen & Güçlü, 2013), it can be thought that it is inevitable for students who cannot manage this process well to experience depression and burnout. Literatürde stress, depresyon ve tükenmişlik düzeyi ile ilgili birçok çalışma vardır. These studies stated that it is necessary to manage stress before reaching the level of depression and burnout (Shapiro et al., 1998; Palmer & Rodger, 2009) and that the situation can be controlled with mindfulness meditations (Ramel et al., 2004; Temel et al., 2007).

Depression is one of the world's most common treatable medical problems, lasting at least two weeks and often longer, and significantly impaired functioning (Ülev, 2014). Depression is an emotional response to ongoing frustration and frustration. Its main characteristic is low self-esteem and mental breakdown (Köroğlu, 2006). It is widespread; its symptoms are many and complex, and it has symptoms that change with age. Depression can occur spontaneously, without a trigger, or as a result of another illness, due to drug use, alcohol use, postpartum, or as a reaction to a challenging life event (Polat & Coşkun, 2020; Aslan, 2018). Freudenberger first introduced the concept of burnout to describe a condition characterized by fatigue, frustration and quitting among volunteer health workers, and Maslach and Jackson later developed it (Freudenberger, 1974; Maslach et al., 1997). Maslach stated that long-term work stress led to burnout and defined it as a professional person's detachment from his profession's original meaning and purpose, not being able to care about the people he/she serves truly. Significant features of burnout include loss of energy, lack of motivation, negative attitude towards others, and actively withdrawing from others (Kaçmaz, 2005).

There are many studies on depression and burnout in the literature. The studies were mainly conducted in the fields of psychology and medicine (Arapcioğlu et al., 2021; Arslan et al., 2018; Alim, 2018; Tunç & Yapıcı, 2019; Tunçel & Süt, 2019). Regarding the field of education, self-esteem (Arslan et al., 2016), anxiety levels (Bozkurt, 2004), self-understanding (Deniz & Sümer, 2010), hopelessness (Çelikel & Erkorkmaz, 2008), physical activity (Yıldırım et al., 2015; Measurer et al., 2015), healthy life (Iskender et al., 2018), social intelligence levels (Doğan, 2006), social media addiction (Balcı & Baloğlu, 2018), Covid-19 (Dikmen, 2021) and stress, locus of control (Akbağ et al., 2005) are available.

There are studies in the literature on music, depression, and burnout. Tuna et al. (2021) examined the effect of music listening preferences of university students on physical activity, depression, and sleep quality and concluded

that rap/hip hop listening provided positive support in three areas. Their study found that participants who received music education had higher levels of personal achievement and lower levels of depression scores, emotional exhaustion, and depersonalization than those who did not. Çolakoğlu and Çapan (2015) examined the burnout levels of music teachers and concluded that there was a significant decrease in teachers' emotional exhaustion and depersonalization scores.

Talışık (2016) stated that music teachers' perceptions of professional efficacy significantly affect their professional satisfaction and burnout. He also stated that they generally experience high burnout levels and feel most inadequate in the learning-teaching process. Kaleli (2021) examined the burnout level of music teachers in the Covid-19 process. The study concluded that teachers' burnout levels were moderate mood disturbance, and burnout levels showed significant differences according to gender, marital status, professional seniority, and school type.

It can be said that the stressful days that start at the entrance stage of graduate education reach the highest level with the course process, the qualification period, the reports of the thesis monitoring committees, and finally, the thesis defense. Students may even have to drop out of their programs in this challenging process. In its report published in 2021, the Council of Higher Education stated that 166,821 students, 147,771 master's and 19,050 doctoral students, were newly enrolled in graduate programs. The same report stated that 60,828 people graduated from master's programs and 7,589 from doctoral programs that year. Looking at the number of students who enrolled and graduated from the programs, it can be said that many students did not complete their programs for various reasons.

The primary purpose of the research is to determine the extent to which all these processes are reflected in the depression and burnout levels of graduate music students. In line with this purpose, the problem statement of the research was determined as follows: How are the depression and burnout levels of graduate students in the field of music? In order to better explain the main problem statement of the research, answers to the following sub-problem statements will be sought.

1. What are the depression levels of the students?
2. What are the burnout levels of the students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between students' burnout levels and their characteristics?
4. Is there a significant relationship between depression and burnout scores?

2. Method

2.1 Study Design

The study's design is a relational survey model examining graduate students' depression and burnout in music. In correlational survey models, the aim is to determine the existence and degree of change between two or more variables. In correlation-type relationship studies, it is tried to learn whether the variables change together or not and, if there is a change together, how it happens. Determining the relationships between variables allows researchers to make predictions about variables (Karasar, 2006; Büyüköztürk et al., 2022).

2.2 Participant

The study group consisted of 236 graduate students who were continuing their master's, doctorate, and proficiency in art education in the field of music in Turkey. Descriptive data of the study group are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Study group

	Group	n	%
Gender	Female	127	53,8
	Male	109	46,2
Age	20-24	74	31,4
	25-28	55	23,3

	29-32	35	14,8
	33- ...	72	30,5
Marital Status	Single	159	67,4
	Married	77	32,6
Education Status	Master Degree	154	65,3
	Ph. D.	70	29,6
	Proficiency in Arts	12	5,1
Having Children Status	Yes	81	34,3
	No	155	65,7
Working Status	Full Time	140	59,3
	Part Time	39	16,5
	Not Working	57	24,2
Institute	Educational Sciences	98	41,5
	Fine Arts	10	4,2
	Social Sciences	28	11,9
	Graduate School	74	31,4
	Music and Fine Arts	26	11
Program	Music Education	105	44,5
	Turkish Music	63	26,7
	Music Performance	44	18,6
	Musicology	8	3,4
	Music Technologies	6	2,5
	Music Theory	5	2,1
	Opera Vocal	5	2,1

As seen in Table 1, the majority of the participants are female. In the age range, 20-24 and 33+ are the most crowded group. Most participants were single, did not have children, were master's students, and actively worked full-time jobs. Most participants (41.5%) are students of the Institute of Educational Sciences and, therefore, of the music education program.

2.3 Data Collection

Researchers need to recognize the characteristic they want to measure well and proceed accordingly (Demirtaş & Özçelik, 2020). In the study, data on the participants' gender, age, marital status, educational status, having children, employment status, institutes, and programs were collected through the "Personal Information Form" developed by the researcher. The questionnaire study can provide definitions by collecting information about demographic characteristics, knowledge, and attitudes (O'Leary, 2017). Attitudes are tendencies that are attributed to an individual and form his/her thoughts, feelings, and behaviors about a psychological object in a traditional way (Kağıtçıbaşı, 2010).

Two data collection tools adapted to Turkish were used in the study. Beck Depression Scale (BDS) was used to determine the level of depression, and Maslach Burnout Inventory -Student Scale (MBI-SS) was used to determine the level of burnout. Permission was obtained from the relevant researchers before the scales were used.

Beck and colleagues developed Beck Depression Scale (BDS) in 1961 to measure behavioral symptoms of depression in adolescents and adults (Beck et al., 1961). In 1978, the scale was revised, duplications defining severity were removed, and patients were asked to mark their condition for the last week, including the present (Guy, 1976). Hisli (1989) and Avşar (2007) conducted Turkish validity and reliability studies of the scale. It is a rating scale consisting of 21 questions and calculated by summing the scores between 0-3 from each answer. Scale values align with the corresponding score ranges 1-10 normal, 11-16 moderate mood disturbance, 17-20 clinically depressed, 21-30 moderately depressed, 31-40 severely depressed, and 41-63 severely depressed (Cihan, 2011). As in the original scale, it consists of 21 items and four sub-dimensions. Avşar (2007) calculated the Cronbach alpha coefficient as .86. In this study, the value is .89.

Maslach Burnout Inventory -Student Scale (MBI-SS) was created by Schaufeli et al. in 2002. Its adaptation into Turkish was made by Çapri et al. (2011). It shows that the 13-item, 3-factor Turkish version of the scale can be used reliably on the university student population (Çapri et al., 2011). The 13-item scale is an adaptation of the general form of the Maslach Burnout Inventory for students (Kaya, 2009). The scale consists of three sub-dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and competence. The scale adaptation study was conducted with 782 students, and exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and test-retest analyses were used. Cronbach alpha coefficient of the scale is .91. The reliability coefficients of the factors are as follows: Emotional Exhaustion .76, Depersonalization .74, and Competence .73. In this study, it was calculated as .65 for the first factor, .64 for the second factor, .71 for the third factor and .74 for the overall scale.

2.4 Data Analysis

The data collected online were entered into the SPSS 26 program. In order to determine the statistical tests to be performed, the data were first checked for normality. For this, normality tests, skewness, and kurtosis values were checked.

Table 2: Normality test results

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Depression	.179	236	.000	.870	236	.000
Burnout	.182	236	.000	.909	236	.000

When the normality test results were examined, it was determined that the data did not show normal distribution ($p < .05$). For this reason, Mann Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis tests, which are non-parametric, were used in the rest of the study. The Mann-Whitney U test is used to test the null hypothesis that "two independent samples come from the same population" without having to assume that the populations from which the sample is drawn are normally distributed (Miller & Miller, 2003).

3. Finding

The findings obtained from the research are explained in order according to the sub-problems. The first sub-problem is as follows "What is the level of depression of the students?" The findings are given in the table below.

Table 3: Beck depression levels

	Group	n	%	Beck result
Gender	Female	127	53,8	11,63
	Male	109	46,2	7,68
Age	20-24	74	31,4	10,32
	25-28	55	23,3	5,73
	29-32	35	14,8	11,8
	33- ...	72	30,5	14,04
Marital Status	Single	159	67,4	7,97
	Married	77	32,6	15,84
Education Status	Master Degree	154	65,3	7,75
	Ph. D.	70	29,6	16,4
	Proficiency in Arts	12	5,1	13,73
Having Children Status	Yes	81	34,3	16,54
	No	155	65,7	4,83
Working Status	Full Time	140	59,3	5,61
	Part Time	39	16,5	10,56
	Not Working	57	24,2	19,1
Institute	Educational Sciences	98	41,5	18,86

	Fine Arts	10	4,2	7,19
	Social Sciences	28	11,9	12,27
	Graduate School	74	31,4	13,09
	Music and Fine Arts	26	11	12,29
Program	Music Education	105	44,5	17,09
	Turkish Music	63	26,7	15,3
	Music Performance	44	18,6	11,16
	Musicology	8	3,4	9,32
	Music Technologies	6	2,5	7,97
	Music Theory	5	2,1	14,97
	Opera Vocal	5	2,1	3,14
Total				11,5

According to the depression scale scores applied to the students, the total score obtained was 11.5. This scoring range indicates that the students have a moderate mood disturbance (Cihan, 2011; Ulaş et al., 2015; Geroğlu et al., 2016; As, 2015).

According to the gender variable, males showed normal symptoms (7.68), while females had moderate mood disturbance (11.63). In the age ranges of 20-24 (10.32), 29-32 (11.8), and 33+ (14.34), moderate mood disturbance was observed, while the values were normal in the 25-28 (5.73) age range. In marital status, those living alone showed normal values (7.97), while the proportion of married people almost reached the clinical depression indicator (15.84).

Across program levels, doctoral students were clinically depressed (16.4). Proficiency in art students was at a moderate mood disturbance (13.73), while master's students were at a normal level (7.75). Students with children were clinically depressed (16.54), while those who did not have children were at a normal level (4.83). When the employment status was analyzed, it was determined that students who were not employed were clinically depressed (19.1). Those working part-time had moderate mood disturbance (10.56), while those working full-time had normal levels (5.61).

When the depression levels according to the institutes are examined, educational sciences are clinically depressed (18.86), while social sciences (12.27), postgraduate education (13.09), and music and fine arts (12.29) institutes are at a moderate mood disturbance. The depression level of fine arts institute students is normal (7.19). In the departments of Turkish music (15.3), music performances (11.16), and music theory (14.97), students have moderate mood disturbance. Music education students were observed to be clinically depressed (17.09). Students in the musicology (9.32), music technology (7.97), and voice education (3.14) departments had normal levels. The findings related to the second sub-problem, "What are the burnout levels of the students?" are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Maslach burnout levels

	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Emotional exhaustion	236	1.2	4.2	2.4	.707
Depersonalization	236	1.00	4.5	2.55	.739
Competence	236	1.75	4.25	2.91	.508
Total	236	1.77	3.85	2.61	.556

The overall mean score of students' burnout levels is 2.61. This result is the value where the score range of 2.61-3.40, which is accepted as the middle level, starts. The burnout levels of graduate students studying in the field of music are at a medium level. In the factors, emotional exhaustion ($\bar{x}$:2.4) and depersonalization ($\bar{x}$:2.55) are low, and competence ($\bar{x}$:2.91) is at a medium level.

The findings related to the third sub-problem, "Do students' burnout levels differ according to their demographic characteristics?" are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U test for the gender and status (Maslach)

		Maslach Burnout Scale					
		Group	n	Emotional exhaustion	Depersonalization	Competence	p
Gender	Female		127	.221	.039	.090	.137
	Male		109				
Marital Status	Single		159	.793	.709	.302	.743
	Married		77				
Having Children Status	Yes		81	.001	.354	.685	.156
	No		155				

Table 5 compares students' burnout scale scores according to gender, marital status, and having children. No significant difference was found in the overall scale scores. In the sub-dimensions, a significant difference was found in the emotional exhaustion dimension of the variable of having children (p=.001).

Figure 1: Mann-Whitney U results

Kruskal Wallis test was applied to determine whether there was a difference between students' age, educational status, study, institute, and department. In order to reveal significant differences between groups, the Mann-Whitney U test was applied between paired groups.

Table 6: Kruskal Wallis test for the age, status, institute and program (Maslach)

	Maslach Burnout Scale			p
	Emotional exhaustion	Depersonalization	Competence	
Age	.024	.859	.042	.683
Education Status	.167	.491	.005	.001
Working Status	.002	.007	.092	.012
Institute	.000	.000	.001	.000
Program	.000	.001	.000	.000

There is no significant difference in the overall scale and sub-factors in the age variable ($p=.683$). There are statistically significant differences in the variables of educational status ($p=.001$), employment status ($p=.012$), institute ($p=.000$), and department ($p=.000$). The first difference is in the competence sub-factor within the educational status ($p=0.005$). A significant difference was found between proficiency in art students and doctoral students ($p=.001$).

There is a significant difference in emotional exhaustion ($p=.002$) and depersonalization ($p=.007$) sub-factors in the employment status variable. In the dimension of emotional exhaustion, there is a difference between non-workers and full-time employees ($p=.001$); in the factor of depersonalization, there is a difference between non-workers and part-time employees ($p=.003$).

There is a statistically significant difference in the institute and department variables. Graduate institute scores showed a significant difference in the emotional exhaustion dimension compared to the others ($p=.001$, $p=.000$, $p=.000$, $p=.000$, $p=.004$). In the depersonalization factor, there is a significant difference between graduate institute-educational sciences ($p=.000$) and graduate institute-fine arts institute ($p=.001$). The difference in the competence factor is between music and fine arts-educational sciences ($p=.004$).

When the relationship between departments was analyzed, it was determined that there were significant differences between music theory and Turkish music ($p=.001$), music theory and music education ($p=.003$), music performances and music education ($p=.000$), and music performances and voice education ($p=.003$).

The findings of the last sub-problem, "Is there a significant relationship between depression and burnout scores?" are given below.

Table 7: Spearman's test result

		Depression	Bournet
Depression	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.450**
	Sig.	.	.000
	n	236	236
Bournet	Correlation Coefficient	.450**	1.000
	Sig.	.000	.
	n	236	236

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

Spearman correlation analysis results are shown above. In the results of the analysis, it was concluded that there was a significant relationship between students' depression scale scores and burnout scale scores.

4. Results and Discussion

The study aimed to determine music graduate students' depression and burnout levels. The study group consisted of 236 graduate music students.

First, the depression levels of the students were determined. The general depression score of 236 students was calculated as 11.5. This score indicates that the students have moderate mood disturbance. In many different studies, it has been determined that the general depression levels of university students are at moderate levels. (Ulaş et al., 2015; Bozkurt, 2004; Deniz & Sümer, 2010; Çelikel & Erkorkmaz, 2008). The depression level of male students was low (7.68), while that of female students was moderate (11.63). Studies in the field support that gender reveals a significant difference in depression (Taytaş & Kardaş, 2022; Özdemir, 2019; Ünal et al., 2002; Akça et al., 2018; Ayas, 2014; Karamustafaalioglu et al., 2004; Baştuğ & Çumraligil, 2004). Although some studies have found that males have higher levels of depression, it can be said that females have higher levels of depression than males.

The study found that students aged 33 and over had the highest level of depression. Studies show that advancing age and stressful life are parallel to depression (Genç et al., 2022; Önal, 2022). The most challenging and complex level of postgraduate education is the doctoral level. The difficulties experienced in this process were reflected in the study's findings. Doctoral students were found to be clinically depressed—studies on the difficulties of the process support this finding (Özmen & Güç, 2013; Sever & Ersoy, 2017; Karadağ & Özdemir, 2017). Students who had children were found to have higher levels of depression. When we consider the time and opportunities parents can allocate to areas such as social, educational, career, and personal development (Tezel & Cevher, 2007), it can be said that the child brings restrictions in many areas of life (Mercan & Şahin, 2017). The responsibility of having children appear to be a factor that increases the depression levels of undergraduate students.

In the postgraduate process, students need support at many points. In this process, in which many sacrifices are made spiritually, financial support is also needed (Aslan, 2007). Students who need more financial support have difficulties in this process and need help to complete their education (Özmen & Güç, 2013). The results obtained from the study are in line with these findings. Students who were not employed were found to be clinically depressed. When the effect of institutes on depression levels was analyzed, it was found that the students of educational sciences institutes were clinically depressed. Similarly, the depression levels of music education students were found to be at the clinical level. This study, conducted among various departments related to the field of music, shows that educational sciences students have higher levels of depression than other students.

It was determined that the general burnout scores of the students were at a moderate level (2.61). This value is at a critical threshold. In this measurement, where the range of 1.81-2.60 points was determined as low level and the range of 2.61-3.40 as medium level, the student's scores increased to the medium level with .1 point. The averages are low in emotional exhaustion and depersonalization sub-dimensions. Maslach et al. (1997) explain emotional exhaustion as a decrease in the emotional and physical resources of the individual. The development of negative attitudes towards work and loss of energy are among the symptoms of emotional exhaustion. Emotional exhaustion is necessary, but more is needed for burnout. Emotional detachment from work due to excessive workload can be considered a prerequisite for depersonalization (Karaaslan et al. 2020). Considering that the emotional exhaustion experienced by the students is related to the learning process, graduate students feel a high level of exhaustion in this sense. The results found for the depersonalization dimension are also low. The depersonalization dimension is considered a reaction to emotional exhaustion (Maslach et al., 1997). Dolunay (2002) explains depersonalization as an individual displaying attitudes and behaviors in a callous manner without considering those affected by the work. Studies show that the depersonalization factor progresses in parallel with the emotional exhaustion factor and that these two factors are at the same levels in determining burnout. The results obtained from the study also bear this similarity.

When we look at different studies conducted in universities, the general burnout level rates are similar to this study (Gündüz et al., 2012; İn & Kula, 2019). It was concluded that exhaustion did not differ significantly on gender, age, and marital status. Significant differences exist in having children, education level, employment status, institute, and department. These results show that burnout is experienced in areas with high levels of depression. There are studies in the literature that gender and age factors do not create a significant difference in burnout (Yenihan et al., 2018; Çapulcuoğlu & Gündüz, 2013). A significant difference was found in the emotional exhaustion dimension of students who had children. Kılıç and Seymen (2011) determined the individual and social causes of burnout as having children and the number of children, over-commitment to work, ego of the individual, personal expectations, and work-related stress. It can be concluded that having children may cause emotional

burnout during graduate education. It was also concluded that students who were not working in any job and had no income also experienced emotional burnout.

Significant differences were found in burnout levels between institutes and departments. Students in educational institutes differed from students in other institutes in all sub-factors. The data obtained from the students in the music theory and music performance departments constitute significant differences.

The research results show that variables with high levels of depression also have high levels of burnout. When the studies in the literature were examined, it was seen that the results obtained from the research overlapped. Based on these results, the suggestions listed below should be considered by all other graduate students in the field of music and by educators involved in the education and training process.

- The advisor-student relationship is the most crucial relationship in which personal intimacy is observed in the graduate education process. For this reason, advisors should observe how their students manage stress while ensuring their academic development. Beyond academic studies, the faculty member who detects a difference in his/her student's behavior or attitudes should provide the necessary guidance when receiving psychological support. In order to increase the awareness of faculty members on this issue, various pieces of training should be given to faculty members who are thesis advisors. This study, in which it was determined that various variables increase depression and burnout levels, is a study in which faculty members can observe their students.
- There are psychological guidance and counseling centers within universities that continue to work actively and that students benefit from free of charge. Department heads should ensure that students benefit from these units.
- Advisors should be actively involved from the beginning to the end of graduate education. Experts should inform students about the program's requirements and the process's psychological effects.
- Students who document their depression or burnout through official health institutions should be given additional time.
- Students' depression and burnout levels should be measured once a year, and the results should be shared with the heads of the relevant departments. In this way, the support students need can be provided.

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